

Supplementary Material A

Figure A1. Global25 similarity map (Ashkenazi_Germany).

Table A1. Top 30 closest modern populations to Ashkenazi_Germany under Global25.

Rank	Population	Distance
1	Maltese	0.0180
2	Italian Calabria	0.0182
3	Italian Campania	0.0207
4	Italian Campania Naples (Campanian)	0.0224
5	Sicilian Syracuse	0.0236
6	Sicilian Trapani	0.0237

Rank	Population	Distance
7	Greek Crete	0.0245
8	Sicilian Central	0.0245
9	Sicilian East	0.0245
10	Italian Calabria (Cosentian)	0.0248
11	Greek Crete Lasithi	0.0251
12	Italian Basilicata (Lucanian)	0.0253
13	Italian Basilicata	0.0253
14	Greek Crete Rethymno	0.0261
15	Sicilian	0.0270
16	Greek Dodecanese Kos	0.0273
17	Greek Kos	0.0273
18	Italian Apulia	0.0278
19	Greek Dodecanese	0.0280
20	Sicilian West	0.0288
21	Italian Apulia (Apulian)	0.0290
22	Greek Cyclades Amorgos	0.0298
23	Greek Crete Chania	0.0307
24	Italian Abruzzo	0.0313
25	Italian Abruzzo (Abruzzese)	0.0313
26	Greek Euboea Central	0.0318
27	Greek Crete Heraklion	0.0321
28	Greek Cyclades Milos	0.0334
29	Italian Campania Salerno (Campanian)	0.0353
30	Italian Molise	0.0353